

THE RISE OF THE IDEAL URBAN CITY MODEL:
AMSTERDAM, NETHERLANDS AND THE EVOLUTION OF SEPHARDIC JEWISH URBAN
DESIGN IN THE GOLDEN AGE

by

Natalya Rowe

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-0117-7978>

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Approved by:

Dr. Paulo Simoes, Department of Honors

Dr. Stacy Mallicoat, Director, University Honors Program

Date:

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Abstract

This project examines the Portuguese Synagogue in Amsterdam, Netherlands as a case study for the impact and development of successful urban planning, and how certain cultural minorities such as Sephardic Jews within the Iberian Peninsula and Latin America shaped the city's geography over time. This research project argues that the exchange between the architecture and materials in the colonies, as well as the Dutch Baroque style, ultimately shapes the Sephardic Jewish community's central synagogue and Jewish Quarter into the ideal urban city model, and ushered the Netherlands into a Golden Age.

This research project is predominantly focused on social and architectural history, specifically within marginalized groups that are often brushed to the outskirts of historical records. The scope of this project falls between the Dutch Golden Age in the Colonial Period. This project uses historiographical, geographical and architectural analysis, and critique of urban development. The intention of this project is to analyze urban planning and how design influences a city's overall economic and social success on the transatlantic world stage, as well as to critique and decolonize former colonial spaces.

Keywords: *Netherlands, Golden Age, colonialism, Sephardic Judaism, religious studies, history*

Literature Review

Amsterdam, the capital of the Netherlands, is the world's leading center of urban transportation. Located in the Northwestern region of Europe, Amsterdam is notable for its development of intricate canal systems, its rich and tolerant culture, and diverse immigration that all help to define the complex ecosystem of Dutch society. The examination of the Dutch Golden Age through to the interwar era, through both a social and urban lens is critical for understanding the influence of minorities within the Netherlands, shaped by many immigrant groups. In this review I will focus on four subsets within the rich history of Amsterdam: its initial development; the city during the Golden Age of the 16-17th centuries, both domestically and abroad; the impact of Jewish culture and peoples on the city; and the modern implications of these historical processes.

Initial Development

Successful surveys of Dutch history largely begin their study during the 16th century shortly after the establishment of the Dutch Republic after its independence from Spain. The subsequent Dutch Golden Age is also a large part of Dutch history, as the power and influence of the Republic reached its peak during this time. Shorto's *Amsterdam: A History of the World's Most Liberal City* is one of the best references for a broad survey of the city, as he breaks his work down by both chronological periods but also by theme, including neighborhood dynamics between Jews and non-Jews, as well as a thorough study of the canal system. Additionally, Arblaster and Lanham's surveys of the Netherlands and Low Countries, while not as specifically focused on the city of Amsterdam, also successfully offer an organized and methodological

outline of the main cultural and historical events of the country. Together, these three works offer a present documentary account of the work surrounding the city and neighborhoods, as analyzed in this research project.

Impact of Jewish Culture and Peoples on the City

This leads researchers to the study of Dutch history in the modern period, which is especially essential to understanding the broader implications and impact on the globalized world both in the past and today. Understanding the geographical and social landscape of the Netherlands can be found in important urban travel books and guides such as *Walking Amsterdam* by National Geographic and even in modern *Amsterdam and the Netherlands* by popular guide Rick Steves. Although published in different decades, they offer a fascinating perspective on the change and continuity of the Netherlands with specific neighborhood views and walkthroughs. Additionally, there are videos and photos in the 20th century that offer a primary source account of the different squares of Amsterdam, which aids in the visual understanding of how people interacted with their city, and also helps provide more resources for understanding its architectural and design developments.

Art, Maps, and Architecture

Much of the history of the synagogues remains available to general audiences today, as Jewish historians worked with synagogues to commemorate their history through the lens of public and art history.¹ This interdisciplinary lens is highly important for the work of this project,

¹ The most up-to-date photographs of the modern city of Amsterdam are from the author as the source, with videos and photos offering a real life glimpse in the world of the Netherlands. The author has primary source videos and photos of the Portuguese Synagogue and Jewish Museum that I intend on utilizing for this research.

as this paper aims to address how the design of the Jewish structures can be linked to economic success and therefore the success of the Netherlands.

It is important to note that these sources of local history (because of their ambiguity on their peer reviewed status) can be unreliable. The author has, to the best of her ability, fact checked these claims via external peer reviewed journals and articles to provide factual information to public records (which are inherently valuable as a social history lens).

The main synagogues addressed in this research project are the Portuguese Synagogue in Amsterdam, Kahal Zur Israel Synagogue in Recife, Brazil, Mikvé Israel-Emanuel Synagogue of Curaçao, and the Shearith Israel Portuguese Synagogue of Manhattan. All of these synagogues are still standing in their original form as mentioned in this paper, with the exception of the New Amsterdam (New York) synagogue, which is supplemented by a map of the location where the original building once stood. This allows for an excellent analysis of the architecture as the building is a primary rather than a secondary source account of the building dimensions.

Additionally, van Nassau of Orange's palace, Mauritshuis, is also another important building as it was the inspiration for the Portuguese Synagogue's architecture. Designed by Jacob van Campen, the leading designer of Dutch Baroque and neoclassical styles, the author will utilize plaques describing the building and selected artworks to both analyze the influence on the Sephardic Jewish community and critique colonialism.

Conclusion

Overall, the development and change of Amsterdam as an urban space, as well as an important location of Jewish history, culture, and influence is a topic that is broad and interdisciplinary, and inspires the need for further research and investigation that will be addressed in this paper.

I.

The history of the Jewish people can be dated back thousands of years, however when considering the lives of Sephardic Jews in the Netherlands and abroad, it is important to retrace their roots back to the Iberian peninsula (modern Spain and Portugal). Sepharad, or Jewish Iberia, was established after the Moorish settlement in the 8th century of Southern Iberia (also called al-Andalus). With this new rule, religious tolerance allowed for Jewish people to have “new possibilities”, such as “community organization and cultural achievement”.² This period dates from the arrival of Jewish people from Palestine after the destruction of the Second Temple.

By the 4th century, the Jews of Sepharad had spread from the coastlines inland, establishing farming communities under the Visigoths.³ During the period between the Visigoth kingdom and Muslim Spain in 711, the Jewish people suffered greatly under measures of persecution and forced conversions. The period of the Muslim occupation of Spain after the Visigoths proved to be a great period for the Spanish Jews, with remarkable growth of Jewish culture and an integration of Jewish people into the larger Jewish diaspora in Sepharad.

This period of growth in Andalusia and Muslim Spain around the 13th and 14th centuries ushered in new architectural forms that can be seen combining traditional Moorish and Spanish styles with Jewish motifs. The thirteenth century was marked by especially beautiful designs, with Toledo being one of the centers of Jewish innovation and culture, south of Madrid.

The Toledo synagogue, known as the church of Santa María la Blanca is one of the oldest synagogues remaining in Europe. Established in 1203, the Toledo Synagogue displays beautiful

² Lacave, J. L., M. Armengol, and F. Ontañón. *Sefarad, Sefarad La España Judía*. Lunwerg Editores, 1999.

³ Lacave 182

Islamic horseshoe arches and patterns, rounded cinquefoils, and Mudéjar column capitals based on Corinthian and Byzantine styles preceding the later Mudéjar style.⁴ Additionally, while the original building was designed as a synagogue, there are elements of the interior design that indicate an Islamic-style influence. For instance, its hypostyle columns indicate a greater influence of mosques, as the covered columns lined up in an orderly row reflect the design of a mosque more closely than a traditional synagogue of the time. Additionally, there is a lack of a women's room typically seen in Orthodox Jewish synagogues.

While Islamic elements are most visibly present in the Toledo synagogue, there are also signs of other influences at play. For instance, the rounded windows and simple exterior are an indicator of a greater European vernacular style of synagogue. The cinquefoils, or five pointed arches, and the blind archway are both Gothic styles that originated in Western Europe.⁵ Finally, there are obvious signs of Jewish influence, such as the inscriptions of Hebrew on the crown molding and Judaic artifacts such as Hebrew tablets and even coins with text in both Hebrew and Arabic, as well as Hebrew and Spanish.

At the height of the Spanish Golden Age, many Jewish scholars and early scientists were appointed to positions of leadership and respect within the Muslim systems of power. For instance, Hasdai Crescas, born in 1340 in Barcelona, was an early Renaissance thinker who applied "Talmudic reasoning" to earlier Aristotelian scientific theories.⁶ As a result, Crescas was a precursor to Galileo's later 16th century contributions to astronomy and physics.

⁴ LaChiusa, Chuck. "Synagogue of Santa Maria La Blanca." *Architecture Around the World*, 2010. <https://buffaloah.com/a/virtual/spain/toledo/maria/maria.html>.

⁵ LaChiusa, Chuck.

⁶ Bacon, Josephine, and Martin Gilbert. *The Illustrated Atlas of Jewish Civilization*. London: Quantum Books, 2007.

It is important to recognize the intercultural elements of al-Andalus and Sepharad during this time. For instance, Christians, Muslims, and Jews all peacefully coexisted and collaborated with each other to build ornate architecture, develop modern science and literature, and most importantly spread and interconnect the cultures together in one efficient society.

The height of Jewish involvement and success in Spain, however, did come to a gradual end with the rise of northern kingdoms determined to expel both Muslims and Jews from Iberia. For instance, in the 15th century the Muslims were targeted for expulsion, as were the Jews of Castille who were banished to *juderías*, akin to Jewish ghettos. They were also barred from practicing certain trades like medicine and forced to wear “badges [designating] them as Jewish”.⁷ This anti—Jewish sentiment culminated in the Massacres of 5151, beginning in 1391 and continuing until 1397. These pogroms occurred on July 6 and spread throughout Spain in waves of violence. Ferrand Martinez, a vehement anti semitic priest, encouraged the people of Seville to destroy synagogues and ghettoize Jewish neighbors.⁸ He intentionally persuaded lower working—class Christians in Andalusia to carry out the crimes, indicating an exploitative nature of Spanish Christians in power— especially monarchs and clergy—to carry out battles over land and power with the guise of a religious war or crusade.

The ostracism and targeting of Jewish people on a local level was made worse by the propaganda of Ferdinand and Isabella during the Reconquista. The consolidation of kingdoms in Iberia, such as Castille and Leon, and later the joint power of Castille and Aragon caused a wave of Christian leadership that made possible the Inquisition of Jewish people. Many Sephardic

⁷ Bacon, Josephine, and Martin Gilbert. 61

⁸ Mindel, Nissan. “The Massacres of 5151 .” Chabad. Accessed March 29, 2024.
https://www.chabad.org/library/article_cdo/aid/112389/jewish/The-Massacres-of-5151.htm.

Jews by the 14th century had fled Iberia out of fear of the growing violence, but many stayed and became *conversos*, also called crypto-Jews or *marranos*.⁹ Conversos, however, were killed by the hundreds, and this led to the eventual expulsion of Jewish people from Iberia.

By 1492, Ferdinand and Isabella issued the *General Edict on the Expulsion of the Jews from Aragon and Castile*, leading to over 100,000 Jewish people fleeing Spain and Portugal, and nearly 50,000 converting to Catholicism. Whether the conversos officially practiced Catholicism out of fear or true belief remains uncertain, as was the number of secretly practicing Jewish people. What is recorded is the official number of openly practicing Jews of Spain by 1492: zero.

Out of the 100,000 Jewish people that fled Spain, some traveled to Portugal in hopes of greater religious tolerance. For a short period, King João II allowed a temporary stay in Portugal, but his successor Manoel I was less willing due to his marriage to Isabella of Aragon (the daughter of Ferdinand and Isabella) placing pressure on the Portuguese crown to aid in the Reconquista. Eventually all Jews were expelled from Portugal, a requirement of his marriage contract to Infanta Isabella of Spain.¹⁰ By 1498, the last remaining Jewish people of Sepharad were banished from the peninsula, where over 25,000 refugees fled to the Netherlands.¹¹ These Jewish people would become the community of Sephardic Jews in the Netherlands. They would bring with them the success of the Spanish Golden Age, and the nature of peace of an interconnected, multi-ethnic, and multicultural community into Amsterdam's newly established and independent economy, assisting in the Golden Age of the Netherlands.

⁹ This term is highly offensive, translating to "pig" in English.

¹⁰Bacon, Josephine, and Martin Gilbert. *The Illustrated Atlas of Jewish Civilization*. London: Quantum Books, 2007, 65

¹¹Bacon, Martin 59.

II.

The Jewish people are historically a migratory group, with persecution as the predominant driving factor for movement. As a result of intolerance of Judaism in many kingdoms around the world, the Jewish people often sought refuge in more tolerant areas, or even established their own settlements seeking religious freedom.

The Sephardic Jewish community, originating from Sepharad, also called the Iberian Peninsula including modern day Spain and Portugal, was the home of many Jewish people for centuries. The kingdoms of Leon and Castille, led by the Catholic majesties Ferdinand and Isabel of Spain led the Reconquista of Southern Spain and expelled both the Jews and Muslims from the Iberian Peninsula in 1492. Some Jews remained in Sepharad as conversos or crypto-Jews, who publicly lived as Catholics, but secretly continued practicing Judaism in the private sphere.

Many Jews, however, fled to the Netherlands due to its religious tolerance of Judaism. The Netherlands, having declared autonomy from Spain and their Catholic influence through the Treaty of Utrecht, was free to accept Sephardic Jews, who often brought over their wealth and knowledge of overseas navigation and trade from Portugal.¹² Additionally, the Sephardic Jews were often excellent merchants due to their ability to speak Spanish, Portuguese, Ladino, and often many more languages. Their ability to communicate in a plethora of languages and dialects allowed for greater communication and networking abroad. Therefore, the Dutch authorities were more inclined to tolerate Judaism within Amsterdam due to the prospect of incoming wealth brought in by the Jewish community.

¹² Shorto, Russell. *Amsterdam: A History of the World's Most Liberal City*. Doubleday, 2013.

The success of Amsterdam's social, economic, and cultural development during the Golden Age is intrinsically tied to the Jewish people then emigrating to the country. As a port city, Amsterdam relied on the economic expertise of international businessmen and negotiators. Jewish immigrants, bringing connections from Hamburg, the Iberian Peninsula, England, and even Latin America to the negotiating table offered a unique advantage that propelled the Netherlands into economic autonomy and success.

The most influential of these immigrant merchants of the Netherlands was Jeronimo Nunes da Costa, a famous ambassador responsible for the connection between Portugal and the Netherlands, as well as an economic trade between England and Holland, despite governmental and military disputes. Da Costa was so influential in the Jewish community that he helped in the sponsorship of the first synagogue within the Netherlands, called the Portuguese Synagogue in Amsterdam. Da Costa's grave was discovered in the Beth Haim Portugees-Israëlietische Begraafplaats (Beth Haim Portuguese Israel Cemetery), where he spent "much time at The Hague acting as Dutch-Portuguese intermediary".¹³ It is here where Da Costa's grave marker can also be seen. It is through this grave marker, alongside his wife, in the most prestigious cemetery for the Dutch Sephardic Jews that historians can conclude that his life was not only highly influential, but he was benevolent enough in his charity work to be honored with a sizable and descriptive monument in his honor, a sign of community respect and care. His life and legacy were so extensive that he was honored in death with a plaque that resembles the Torah, the highest and holiest scripture in the Jewish faith. It is evident in life and death that Jeronimo

¹³"Moses 'Jeronimo Nunes Da Costa' Curiel." Find a Grave. Accessed May 17, 2024. <https://www.findagrave.com/memorial/128452501/moses-curiel#>.

Nunes da Costa was a man of great pride for the Sephardic Jewish community, and can be considered an ideal representative of the small but economically successful migrant group.

The two most influential sources used in this research is the book *The Portuguese Synagogue in Amsterdam* and the article, *The Architectural Origins of the Great Early Modern Urban Synagogue*. The book is published by Amsterdam's Ministry of Education, and is by far the greatest wealth of information regarding everything pertaining to the Esnoga, including architecture, the Sephardic influence, and it even mentions Moses Curiel (the Hebrew name for Jeronimo Nunes da Costa) laying the first bricks of the synagogue, further proving his civic and economic importance.¹⁴ This reference book was sold by the museum itself, which could potentially lead to some bias in terms of the source material. However, it is highly objective and accurate, although obviously proud of such a feat of architecture. *The Architectural Origins of the Great Early Modern Urban Synagogue* is a peer reviewed source that examines pre-1700 architectural styles of synagogues, both in Western and Eastern Europe. For the scope of this project, only the Western European architectural analysis will be interpreted. Overall, both works are incredibly valuable secondary source accounts of the architecture of Amsterdam and will provide strong resource material.

The impact of Jews within the Netherlands and the Dutch colonies was great, and is further explored within the greater sources of Dutch ethnic history. For instance, there are numerous accounts of the exploration of the Dutch West and East Indies companies, the official colonial companies responsible for colonial imports and economic endeavors from the

¹⁴ Pieter Vlaardingbroek. *The Portuguese Synagogue in Amsterdam*. Cultural Heritage Agency, Ministry of Education, Culture, and Science, 2020, 23.

Netherlands. In *Communities of port Jews and their Contacts in the Dutch Atlantic World*, author Klooster explores the term “port-Jews”, or the Jews who lived a life of travel, exploration, and in pursuit of economic success as a result of increasing Dutch colonial endeavors.¹⁵ In this study, Recife in Brazil and Willemstad in Curaçao are the central cities examined. It is important to note that the author described the Jews of New Amsterdam, or later New York, as “commercially” unimportant to the Netherlands, and chooses to not discuss them. In this paper, the Jewish community of New Amsterdam *will* be discussed as an important congregation influenced by the work of de Fonseca, the Brazilian rabbi whose congregation would later build both the New Amsterdam and the Dutch Portuguese Synagogue.

In addition, the triangular trade of Brazil, Portugal, and Amsterdam is further explored through the trans-Atlantic trade of Jeronimo Nunes da Costa and crypto-Jews, or Sephardic Jews who converted to Christianity as a means of survival from the Iberian expulsion and murder of Jews. When considering the economic success of Sephardic Jews in the West and East Indies Companies, it is critical to reference Jonathan Israel, the world renowned author and expert of the Dutch Golden Age and the Jewish involvement in the period. In fact, he is even referenced in the aforementioned article. In this research, Israel’s work, *The Economic Contribution of Dutch Sephardi Jewry to Holland’s Golden Age*, will be utilized as a core material of this work.

It is important to note that the economic success of the Netherlands was also at the expense of others, notably indigenous and African people who were enslaved and killed. The Sephardic Jewish involvement in these acts is complex, as “almost the whole distribution of

¹⁵ Klooster, Wim. “Communities of Port Jews and Their Contacts in the Dutch Atlantic World.” *Jewish History* 20, no. 2 (2006): 129–45. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/20100975>.

Portuguese East Indian spices and Brazil sugar to northern Europe was handled by the Portuguese New Christians ... residing" in the Low Countries, but they also were victims of oppression themselves.¹⁶ While Jewish people were certainly a minority in the broader Dutch Calvinist landscape, they also had and continue to have a large role in the responsibility and accountability in the hierarchical power structure of oppression and enslavement of indigenous and African people.

It is critical to remember that sugar (mostly from Brazil) and spices such as nutmeg from the Banda Islands were exploited as a result of violence and oppression.¹⁷

The Sephardic Jewish community in the Netherlands would play an important role in the Dutch colonial projects. This essay predominantly focuses on the Western Dutch colonial projects, including Recife, Curaçao, and New Amsterdam. After the Sephardic Jewish migration to the Netherlands, a number of members decided to participate in the international trade and settlements abroad.¹⁸

The discussion of the Netherlands' colonial project begins with the creation of the Dutch East and West Indies Companies. After the 1579 Treaty of Utrecht, and later, at the end of the

¹⁶ The economic contribution of Dutch Sephardi Jewry to Holland's Golden Age, 1595-1713," in: idem, ed Empires and Entrepots: The Dutch, the Spanish Monarchy, and the Jew

¹⁷"The Massacre of the Bandanese." Histori Bersama. Accessed February 27, 2024.
<https://historibersama.com/the-massacre-of-the-bandanese-tirto/>.

¹⁸ It is important to note that there is no "linear" path the entirety of the Sephardic Jewish community took in regards to migration. Like any community, individual and family preferences and needs were a decisive factor that ultimately decided the route and journey. Of the 25,000 Sephardic Jewish people that fled to the Netherlands, some decided to stay and not participate in colonialism. Others traveled to Recife, Brazil, and returned back to Amsterdam. Others would continue on to the Caribbean and even to North America. Each person's story is exceptionally unique, and it is important to acknowledge that the community held a diverse array of motivations to travel, causing a difference in how they migrated.

Eighty Years War in 1648, the Dutch were free from Spanish control. This conflict was not only one of military intervention, but also of economic competition. Spices such as nutmeg and pepper were previously held by the Portuguese monopoly. However, by the turn of the 17th century, many Dutch naval fleets were successful in their acquisition of valued goods.¹⁹ This explosion of naval ability and potential for financial success created an intense opportunity for Dutch merchants, leading to the formation of the Vereenigde Oost-Indische Compagnie (VOC) in 1602.

The size and power of the VOC cannot be underestimated. The monopoly made treaties with Asian leaders, controlled the waterways east of Europe, and even committed acts of genocide, which will be further explored in this research. The VOC dominated the European colonial zones for nearly 200 years, expanding its authority and influence to numerous locations. The Heeren Segentien, or board of directors, delegated daily affairs, and expansionism, and controlled the first international company until the end of the Dutch Golden Age.²⁰

In 1621, the States General under the United Provinces of the Netherlands, approved the 24 year charter, creating the Dutch West Indies Company.²¹ Spanning over part of the continents of Africa and Latin America, it was clear that the VOC's financial success propelled the Netherlands to search for further colonial projects. This search transformed the West Indies Company into an extending arm of the VOC into Brazil, Curaçao, and later, North America.

¹⁹ *VOC – United Dutch East India Company*. Western Australian Museum.
<https://museum.wa.gov.au/explore/dirk-hartog/voc-united-dutch-east-india-company>

²⁰ *VOC – United Dutch East India Company*. Western Australian Museum.
<https://museum.wa.gov.au/explore/dirk-hartog/voc-united-dutch-east-india-company>

²¹ "Prosperity of the West India Company." The Library of Congress. Accessed April 15, 2024.
<https://www.loc.gov/item/2021666729/>.

Without the VOC, or the West Indies Company, colonialism would've been conducted by private companies or people. Instead, Dutch colonialism amounted to a much larger systemic/state sponsored program, shifting the project from one directed by individual investors, (who also played a role in a larger framework). It is also the VOC and West Indies Company that enabled the Jewish persons to travel abroad due to the government's official policy of religious tolerance. It is difficult to determine whether the Jewish community would have participated in colonization if such projects were privately operated as opposed to a joint measure of company and state sponsored influence.

Experimentation with Jewish-Dutch architecture was also widely carried out in the colonies of the Netherlands. The first major Dutch urban colony was in Recife, Brazil. Here we see the first experimentation with city planning, which had significant contributions to Jewish settlement. Located on the eastern coast, Recife was highly sought out by the West India Company due to its geographical connection between the Americas and Europe, as well as its profitable sugarcane industry, a booming cash crop that held much enthusiasm from its European audience.

The arrival of the Dutch in Brazil under Nassau-Siegen in 1637 marked the beginning of Dutch colonialism, of which the Iberian Jews greatly benefitted from. It is also here where Jewish-Dutch architecture can be seen taking a vernacular angle, as seen in the Kahal Kadosh Zur Israel synagogue, which drew upon elements of local building materials and painting supplies. The Dutch ruled Recife from 1630 to 1654, when the Portuguese eventually reclaimed the colony, forcing the Dutch Jews to scatter again.

It is important to note that Brazil's Recife congregation was developed after the city had already been designed and built, essentially forcing the community to squeeze into buildings—mostly businesses—that were not intended as places of worship. Issac Aboab da Fonseca, the rabbi of the Brazilian congregation, returned to Amsterdam after the Portuguese invasion of Recife in 1654, and was a key designer and advocate for the building of the Dutch Esnoga, which opened in 1675. A key difference between the two synagogues is the size and placement of the building in relation to the surrounding city. Recife's synagogue was cramped between two buildings, unable to expand or accommodate a growing community. Da Fonseca actively shaped the Esnoga to include two stories, a private courtyard, and the neighboring block to be a Jewish neighborhood as a means of correcting this issue experienced in Brazil. In many ways, Recife was a testing ground for the Sephardic Jewish people in the Netherlands to determine what was successful (or consequently unsuccessful) in the design of an urban place of worship and community.

From Recife, many Jews went to Curaçao in the Caribbean, where the vernacular Mikvé Israel-Emanuel Synagogue was established in 1674, also following a similar design strategy to Recife's. Curaçao's synagogue, like the Esnoga, was also a free standing building that allowed for the greater accommodation of an increase of Jews.

Voyaging from Recife to Holland's North American colony, the first boat to New Amsterdam carried only 23 Jews, all of whom were Sephardic. As the name suggests, the New Amsterdam colony was owned by the Netherlands (in what is modern day Manhattan). The Jews experienced rejection when they docked the ship *Sainte Catherine*, as the Governor of New Amsterdam, Peter Stuyvesant, rejected their immigration into the colony under an anti-Semitic

rationale.²² Despite this, the Jewish people overcame this trouble by writing to the Dutch West India Company, which ultimately had a greater authority to grant tolerance in the colony than the governor. Again, it is evident that the power of the VOC and its extending companies granted Sephardic Jews privileges in economic and community based endeavors, allowing them to reach success unimaginable on the Iberian Peninsula.

The endurance of hardship faced through immigration and the building of community support and refuge is a strongly American theme represented by the Statue of Liberty. Emma Lazarus, a direct descendant of one of the original Sephardic Jews on the first ship to New Amsterdam, would write the famous poem “The New Colossus”, which is engraved in bronze on the bottom of the Statue of Liberty.²³ The Statue, located near Ellis Island- the center of immigration of the East Coast, and especially for later Jewish immigrants- is a reminder of hope, encouragement, and endurance despite the difficulties of moving abroad. Lazarus’s poem is also a symbol of hope for the Jewish community, as the small and often discriminated group was able

²² “Introduction: Origins of the American Jewish Community.” Jewish Women’s Archive. Accessed October 31, 2023. <https://jwa.org/article/introduction-origins-of-american-jewish-community>.

²³ Not like the brazen giant of Greek fame,
 With conquering limbs astride from land to land;
 Here at our sea-washed, sunset gates shall stand
 A mighty woman with a torch, whose flame
 Is the imprisoned lightning, and her name
 Mother of Exiles. From her beacon-hand
 Glows world-wide welcome; her mild eyes command
 The air-bridged harbor that twin cities frame.
 “Keep, ancient lands, your storied pomp!” cries she
 With silent lips. “Give me your tired, your poor,
 Your huddled masses yearning to breathe free,
 The wretched refuse of your teeming shore.
 Send these, the homeless, tempest-tost to me,
 I lift my lamp beside the golden door!”

to make history and be acknowledged for their positive influence on the shaping of their new country.

It is evident that the Sephardic Jews broadly shaped the future of every country they lived in, but especially the United States. For instance, one of the greatest financiers of the Revolutionary War was Haym Salomon. Salomon was a Portuguese- Polish immigrant of Sephardic descent who financially contributed to George Washington's army, ultimately leading to the success and sovereignty of the 13 Colonies as the United States. Additionally, Salomon financially contributed to the oldest synagogue in Philadelphia, Mikveh Israel.

The Sephardic Jewish community in Holland was also financially supportive of the urban expansion of architecture that accompanied their growing immigrant population. The first synagogue in the Netherlands was a Sephardic synagogue called the Beth Israel-Portuguese Synagogue, and was funded by the community, as well as by Jeronimo Nunes da Costa, an influential Portuguese-Jewish merchant marked by his success in international trade.

After the Sephardic Jews in Brazil returned back to Amsterdam in 1654, many were inspired to create a grand synagogue, supplemented by a supportive surrounding courtyard and Jewish quarter to create a permanent community for the Jewish people. The Portuguese Synagogue was designed shortly after the return of the Sephardic congregation from Brazil, led by Issac Aboab da Fonseca, who attempted to correct the mistakes of Recife's temple in Amsterdam. This led to a unique and functional synagogue in the heart of Amsterdam that proved to be extremely successful in its design.

The Portuguese Synagogue is especially unique in its architecture as it doesn't follow the traditional design elements of the Golden Age. In the Early Modern period, the traditional

synagogue was a small, vernacular building- meaning it adhered to the traditional design elements and architectural style of the local buildings. This indicates that the Jewish attendees of the synagogue would not be inclined to draw unwanted attention to themselves, but instead blend into their surroundings. Another form of protection Jews were keen on implementing was the use of Christian church- looking buildings as Jewish religious meeting places. Protestant churches were considered acceptable by the Dutch government and people, as the majority of the population was Protestant (most were Calvinist). Therefore to prevent the targeting of their places of worship, many Jewish communities opted to preserve the Christian-like facade of their buildings (often Protestant churches were also rented to Jewish congregations).

The Portuguese Synagogue, also referred to as the Esnoga, is an outlier to these typical practices of synagogue design, as its architecture can be classified as Dutch Baroque instead of vernacular or Christian. The building was completed in the late 1670s, and was built in the style of van Nassau's palace, Mauritshuis, to honor the prince due to his religious tolerance.²⁴ Elements of the synagogue include tall, vertical pillars, steeples, ornate gables, and it is designed to be viewed overall as opulent and distinctive among other less ornate structures. Many design elements found in the Toledo synagogue in Spain are evident in the blended architectural style of the Esnoga, drawing upon the same style of columns among other stylistic designs.

Daniel Stalpaert, the first city planner for Amsterdam, can be credited with creating the major canal systems and overall city's layout of the sidewalks and streets. Stalpaert designed the *Map of Amsterdam with the New Enlargement*, arguably one of the most important maps of Amsterdam, which is still used today. He also designed the Portuguese Synagogue, inspired by

²⁴ The Nassau-Orange House is a key component of early modern Dutch history, as this House was in command during the time of the victory in the 80 Years' War, independence from Spain, and the unification of the Netherlands.

his colleague Jacob van Campen's design of the Mauritshuis. His construction of Dam Square is the most notable work after the Portuguese synagogue, and his involvement in the establishment of warehouses for the Dutch East India Company is also relevant to Sephardic Jewish participation in colonial trade and expansion.

It is during this time that a split occurred between the Ashkenazi and Sephardic communities in Amsterdam that highlights their differences in religious expression, culture, and languages reflected in their architecture. The two Jewish communities converged into the Netherlands. However, this did not automatically imply a cultural connection or coalition between the groups. In many circumstances, Sephardic and Ashkenazi Jews were rivals seeking out the same resources and land. It is evident in the Jewish Cultural Quarter that the two distinct groups were placed in proximity to each other (in fact, across the street in plain view of each other's synagogues) creating competition. Essentially, Sephardic Jews held a larger overarching goal to rebuild Sepharad while simultaneously assimilating into Dutch culture.

New philosophical thought led by Sephardic Jewish philosopher Baruch Spinoza cleared the way for not only new political thought, but also drew controversy within the Sephardic community.²⁵ Under his Hebrew name, Baruch Spinoza, he questioned the authority and rabbinical teachings of the congregation, until Issac Aboab da Fonseca and other leaders of the Sephardic Jewish council excommunicated him. Spinoza's personal story reflects a narrative that while Sephardic Jews were flexible in certain regards such as immigration and language, they were rigid in their understanding of religious doctrine and had traditions to uphold through

²⁵ Damasio, Antonio R. *Looking for Spinoza: Joy, Sorrow, and the Feeling Brain*. London: Vintage, 2004.

religious teaching. Spinoza, on a grander scale, also reflects the growing period of Rationalism, and later the Enlightenment, which prioritized logical, deductive reasoning over blind faith.

The largest group of Jews to arrive in the Netherlands was the Sephardic Jews, until the Chmielnicki Uprising in modern Ukraine and Lithuania in 1648 where Eastern European Jews were forced to flee westward, when many arrived in Amsterdam. There was a considerable difference between Sephardic and Ashkenazi Jews, marked by stereotypes and misconceptions between each other. The Ashkenazi Jews were considered poorer than the Sephardic, as they were often refugees fleeing the East. Sephardic Jews, who were often trying to assimilate into Dutch culture and be tolerated as a religiously and culturally accepted minority, isolated themselves from the Ashkenazic Jews.²⁶

This difference in Ashkenazim and Sephardim led to a difference in architecture. For instance, the Esnoga was “significantly larger” than the neighboring vernacular Ashkenazi temple, which was visible on the street and often required walking on public roads to get to a different location within the synagogue. The Sephardic Esnoga was self-contained in a large courtyard.²⁷ While it is incredibly important to study Ashkenazi history, this project will focus predominantly on the Sephardic-Jewish experience, and their lasting impacts, as it is equally essential to question the *Ashkenonormativity* of modern Jewish history and amplify the story of Sephardic Jews—a minority within the already small Jewish minority.

²⁶ This stereotype of poor Ashkenazi Jews and wealthy Sephardic Jews is still perpetuated to the present. This bias has created divisions within the Jewish community itself, as it began in Amsterdam. Many Jewish people are working to dismantle these harmful stereotypes, arguably embedded in anti semitic roots.

²⁷ ResearchGate. “The Architectural Origins of the Great Early Modern Urban Synagogue.” Accessed September 21, 2023.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/275138818_The_Architectural_Origins_of_the_Great_Early_Modern_Urban_Synagogue.

It can be concluded that a large portion of the Sephardic Jewish success in the Netherlands and its colonies is directly tied to their commercial trading and business. The Sephardic Jews are responsible for a great deal of trade connections between Europe and the American continents, which brought further prosperity to the Netherlands and its capital, Amsterdam. A measure of their success can be seen in the synagogues and other structures built during this time.

III.

The Netherlands is widely acknowledged as the world's most liberal country, and with legal prostitution, recreational marijuana use, and the Court of International Justice, this claim holds a legitimate argument.²⁸ While these facts are indisputable, there is a much sinister and lingering colonial history of the Netherlands that is equally important, yet much less discussed due to "color blindness".²⁹ This paper will reference Chimamanda Adichie's concept of a "single story" narrative within the Netherlands to describe and dismantle how the Dutch perpetuate neocolonialism and white supremacy in the Netherlands through visual elements such as advertisements and written language. Ultimately, there must be a change in how history is taught and understood to dismantle colonialism and white supremacy.

The history of colonialism is told through a single story lens, without deconstructing and dismantling the problematic rhetoric (or lack thereof) surrounding people's lives. The single story lens, or only offering one perspective that is often a stereotype, dehumanizes the lived experiences of marginalized communities, and leaves these groups vulnerable to exploitation and oppression from lingering power dynamics- especially white supremacy and patriarchy. This fails to allow new generations to learn and grow from the past colonial experiences and develop a more just nation.

The Dutch have an extensive history with colonialism, tracing back over four hundred years. bell hooks describes this lack of reckoning with the past as a part of "mass culture

²⁸ Shorto, 2014

²⁹ Hooks, 1992.

[including] imperialist nostalgia tak[ing] the form of reenacting and re ritualizing in different ways the imperialist, colonizing journey as narrative fantasy of power and desire, of seduction by the Other”.³⁰ Imperialist nostalgia is the collective refusal to acknowledge that the past might not have been the idyllic Golden Age so widely perpetuated, but instead had harmful effects on those who were exploited for the wealth of the Dutch elite. It is also important to understand the description of Othering, “where the more powerful member of a binary pair —masculinity, whiteness—is consistently bracketed and is thereby invisibilized and installed as the norm”.³¹ In binary systems- patriarchy, gender, white supremacy, and colonialism- the categorization and division of people based on constructed groups is detrimental to equality and equity. Despite being socially manufactured categories, “race, like gender, is ‘real’ in the sense that it has real, though changing, effects in the world and real, tangible, and complex impacts on individuals’ sense of self and life chances”.³² This essentially means that socially constructed identities still have meaning if the power structure in place acknowledges and enforces these dynamics- perpetuating neocolonialism.

It is important to note that “the complexity of racial-ethnic-religious processes of Othering and dehumanization are not unique to Europe, after all we are all interconnected in global constellations of racial and cultural hierarchies, which are regionally and locally shaped”.³³ This means that discrimination, prejudice, and racism are not solely a European issue, as evident by colorism in Latin America, hate crimes in America, and so on. However, the scope of this paper will be limited to the Netherlands, in the European Union.

³⁰ Hooks, 1992.

³¹ Wekker and Lutz 2001

³² Frankenberg 1993, 11

³³ Essed and Trienekens 2007

Colonialism, or the practice of exploiting and controlling an outside territory for the economic and political benefit of another nation, has been argued to be “over” in the modern world.³⁴ While colonialism might not look the same as it did in the 19th century, it is evident that a new form of colonialism has arisen, called neocolonialism. Neocolonialism, according to J.R. Chavez states that while “newly independent nations might be politically free, [they] remain subordinate, especially economically, to the former metropolis or another power”.³⁵ Different forms of neocolonialism can be found in different sectors of popular culture, and the “degree of domination varies by time, locale, gender, class, and other factors such as the presence of additional ethnic groups, which create complex hierarchies” (Chavez, 2011). This dismisses the idea that color blindness is acceptable, as racism and colonialism manifest differently depending on which geographical region it is in.

For instance, “there is the whiteness of the Dutch Art sector, where art with a capital A stands for white, Dutch, European”.³⁶ One of the largest art museums in Amsterdam is the Rijksmuseum, which is dedicated to preserving and collecting the artwork of the Dutch past. The museum is massive, and located centrally in the city near other popular tourist attractions, such as the van Gogh museum, which further encourages locals and tourists alike to visit. Despite its grandeur and prestige, such as its vast collection of Rembrandts, with half a dozen rooms dedicated to nautical expertise and the glorification of overseas travel, there is no room dedicated to the lived experiences of those who were colonized. As of 2024, there was one single room at the back of the Rijksmuseum housing the objects of Indonesian and Japanese people, and

³⁴ This is clearly a false narrative, as it is evident that the world’s leading countries such as the United States still control Puerto Rico, Guam, and have forcibly annexed Hawai’i and Alaska without the consent of the indigenous peoples. However, there is a lack of discourse within the U.S. government about their modern imperialism

³⁵ Chavez

³⁶ Essed and Trienekens

nothing about Caribbean, Brazilian, or indigenous people who were also victims of the Dutch East India Company and the Dutch West India Company. The only information about Brazil was an illustrated book about exotic animals, suggesting a single story narrative of Brazil as foreign, wild, and ultimately painting its people as subhuman.

To expound upon this discovery, the online Exhibit of Slavery, which used to be a temporary in person exhibition, was taken down last year and digitized in an online collection.³⁷ This exhibition's problematic nature is twofold: both the way the exhibit is assembled and the content itself. Firstly, there are only ten objects described to be connected to slavery, but in reality every single object in the Rijksmuseum has a connection to slavery. This undermines the insidious nature of museum collections and downplays the dark nature of colonialism stealing indigenous treasure for their own benefit. This double discourse of discussing racism, but watering down its truly vile nature is an expression of "white guilt", which is "how [white people] confess shame, or, the other way round, deny racism, absolve themselves from responsibility for existing racial injustices, or express discomfort at the idea of white identity".³⁸ The Rijksmuseum's temporary exhibit is simply an expression of this absolution from responsibility, as they have made no strides to decolonize the museum or add more diverse voices to the conversation to hear the input of communities devastated by colonialism. The lack of advertising in the digital archive signals where the priorities of the Rijksmuseum fall: preformative and incomplete. This is how neo colonialism operates: by benefitting from the ticket sales but yet refusing to acknowledge formally and permanently the very real and persistent damage they have committed by exploiting objects that do not belong to them and

³⁷ Rijksmuseum

³⁸ Essed and Trienekens

glorifying the violent past. This responsibility of fostering an exhibit of an unglorified past falls onto the Dutch government, which partially funds these exhibits.

Secondly, the objects within the slavery exhibition themselves are problematic. For instance, there is the *Still Life with a Turkey Pie*, painted by Pieter Claesz in 1627. This oil painting is undoubtedly beautiful to the eye, and its composition is clearly an example of Dutch still life, which set the course of European and modern art towards an analysis of color, form, and how light interacts on objects. These paintings are seemingly harmless, if not inspirational, as artists such as Cezanne, Monet, and van Gogh further expanded upon these compositions into Impressionism and Expressionism.

However, this particular painting is interesting because its subjects display traditional Dutch foods, which are a key to understanding the culture of the time. In this painting, nutmeg can be found. In the official Rijksmuseum analysis of this painting, they stated that “the spices used in this pie were obtained by the Dutch East India Company (VOC), often through violence and slavery. Nutmeg, for example, came from the Banda Islands, part of the Maluku Archipelago. The Dutch took these islands by force in 1621. Enslaved people had to cultivate and harvest the nutmeg”.³⁹ Not only does this language downplay the atrocities that occurred, but it normalizes the whitewashing of history. According to Histori Bersama, a historical website written and translated by Indonesian scholars, the massacre of the Banda Islands was not simply one of vague “force”, instead declaring that “chaos was unavoidable as the VOC responded harshly, cruelly even. Inhabitants were slaughtered mercilessly...approximately only 300 people managed to escape.”⁴⁰ They also describe how victims were decapitated and mutilated by the

³⁹ Rijksmuseum

⁴⁰ Raditya and Raryarasm

Dutch VOC, which comes without acknowledgement or apology from the current Dutch museums. The difference in language is a key indicator that the Rijksmuseum is complicit in upholding colonialism, which can only be dismantled by listening to and sharing the stories of those who were impacted- in this case, the Indonesian people.

Neocolonialism is not only evident in museums, but in all forms of visual media and advertising. For instance, La Drogheria is the most common brand of spices in Albert Heijn, the largest chain grocery store in the Netherlands.⁴¹ The emblem on the front of the pepper and nutmeg containers is a sailing ship, similar to the ones from the 17th century Golden Age. This is problematic because consumers are often choosing this brand of spices, even seen in international hostels and the University of Amsterdam, and many do not make the connection between subversive images of colonialism in their own space and how this is normalizing the notion of glorifying imperialism through underlying messaging that is rarely challenged or acknowledged. It is also relevant to note that Venice was an equally vital trading port similar to the Netherlands, of which they exchanged ideas in the Renaissance and Northern Renaissance, which explains the Italian name of La Drogheria.

Public advertisements are also examples of how neo colonialism and exploitation of the former colonies is normalized. The Westermarkt and Jan van Galenstraat tram stops are advertised as cheap trips to Curaçao and Belize, both of which are former Dutch and French colonies. Both tram stops' advertisements had to be approved by the Gemeentelijk Vervoerbedrijf (GVB), the official Dutch intercity transportation agency, to be placed there: meaning that there is some legitimate Dutch office acknowledging and accepting the exploitation

⁴¹ Albert Heijn

of the two nations. This refers back to bell hooks's theory in *Eating the Other*, as "non-white people have their best qualities taken and used, while their entire self is discarded and not wanted in a white capitalist space". Additionally, the concept of agency is taken into account here, as the people who currently live in Belize and Curacao might feel similarly to those also oppressed during the age of empire, such as Hawai'i, who also want their land reclaimed from white tourism and colonization. The lack of agency indigenous people have to make decisions regarding their land is another example of modern neocolonialism. Increasingly made clear, land acknowledgements are simply not enough (which the Netherlands is currently not even doing) but reparations and respect for a nation's sovereignty and agency must also occur. The first steps to this process would be a formal acknowledgement of the Dutch government for their involvement in imperialism.

The issue with these seemingly innocent signs is that it relies on Wekker's concept of white innocence, which "encapsulates a dominant way in which the Dutch think of themselves, as being a small, but just, ethical nation; colorblind, thus free of racism; as being inherently on the moral and ethical high ground, thus a guiding light to other folks and nations".⁴² These street signs and advertisements, in reality, are perpetuating the notion that the Netherlands does not need to change, and many Dutch people stubbornly will not let go of the harmful colonial past, intertwining colonial glorification with a sense of nationalism or culture.

There is a growing discourse on the ways in which people can dismantle colonialism in the Netherlands. For instance, the World Museum in Amsterdam has placed a strong emphasis on decolonizing its collection and space, and even changed its name from the Trophen Museum,

⁴² Wekker

(meaning tropics or tropical in English). The act of “decolonizing is a practice aimed at rethinking heritage in a way that exposes such processes of power (as well as otherness, or alterity) in order to foster more equal and just societies and connections, even if a truly just society is hard, if not impossible, to achieve”.⁴³ It is incredibly important to understand that the way art is both displayed in a museum and how the museum depicts the artwork are both essential to decolonizing a space. Artwork, especially ethnographic artwork, cannot favor or glorify the past, but instead must be an accurate reflection of the real lived experiences of those under occupation and oppression. This work is oftentimes very difficult for museum curators, especially if the academic institutions do not educate their students on the importance of acknowledging the dark past of ethnographic objects.

There is much debate about the future of decolonization. Wekker argues that the work of “historians should ‘attempt a critical, intersectional, and decolonial reading of white Dutch self-representation, with special attention to the ways in which the racial economy, with its gendered, sexualized, and classed intersections, continues to underwrite dominant, racist ways of knowing and feeling’”.⁴⁴ An intersectional approach is undoubtedly the only way forward, and it is the responsibility of historians like myself to continuously decolonize my perception of history and understanding of the world. While the future is unclear, there is hope to be found when seeing the work of many radically different scholars dismantling the systems of oppression for everyone to be uplifted- both in the Netherlands and abroad.

⁴³ van Huis

⁴⁴ Wekker

The exploration of Sephardic Jewish interactions in the colonial holdings and its reflection onto architecture is part of a larger dialogue of race, power, and structural inequality. When considering the experience of Sephardic Jews, both in the Netherlands and in the colonial holdings, it is essential to question their position in the greater racial hierarchy. The understanding of Jewishness today can be defined as an ethno-religion, and has drawn away from the racially constructed understanding defined by 20th century eugenics and racial policies such as Nuremberg Laws. Understanding where and how Jewish identity fits within the broader, colonial landscape is complex, and difficult to ascertain concretely. What is important to understand and recognize is that Sephardic Jews collaborated in and alongside the colonial project of the Dutch Empire. While a historically marginalized minority and “othered” by Protestant – Dutch natives, a significant amount of this community voyaged to Recife, Curaçao, and New Amsterdam as a method of gaining social influence and financial success, even arguably through directly exploitive means, such as the capture of indigenous land with the goal of establishing settlements.

Jewish land usage is particularly interesting, as a core tenet of Judaism concretely establishes strict matrilineal definitions of the Jewish soul, therefore negating the desire or need for proselytizing commonly found in Protestant and Christian faiths. In essence, with an exclusionary enclosed faith and culture, it is evident that the Jewish people do not have the same colonial goals of spreading doctrine or modeling cities after white Protestant holdings in the

traditional sense, but rather operated as a private sect that also circumstantially profits from colonization.

There is a greater dialogue to be had, regarding the “why” inquiry surrounding the Jewish involvement in Dutch international colonialism. This paper has clearly described that Sephardic Jews fit the criteria of excellent international tradespeople, with a plethora of languages spoken, centuries of experience coexisting among diverse and varying cultures (such as Mujédar Spain).

There is also a much deeper conversation about the racial hierarchy and subsequent power dynamic of the Golden Age. In the height of colonialism, western European men of a wealthy lineage held the normative position of power. In many circumstances, minorities historically have attempted to work within the system of the white supremacist, patriarchy by ostracizing and oppressing other minority groups, with the hopes of assimilating or being more closely perceived as white as opposed to dismantling the entire system altogether.

In the case of Jews abroad, it is difficult to pinpoint the motivations as to why they actively participated in a larger system that caused so much death and pain. Undoubtedly, economic opportunities certainly played a significant role. The author plans to continue exploring this larger question and continuing research.

Conclusion

The importance of this research cannot be underestimated. In an ever-globalizing world, establishing connections between the diverse lived experiences of migrants and the shifting nature of cities is essential to contextualizing modern urban landscapes and their respective architecture.

Colonialism and the age of imperialism have rightly been examined with increasing scrutiny by higher academia. Its consequences, widely spread and harshly imposed, must be analyzed with a critical eye to the status quo of former historical analysis of colonization – Eurocentric and propagandized. This mentality has only begun to take on a systemic and institutional level, such as the Tropen Museum changing its name to the Wereld Museum in 2024. Even then, the highly tourist attracting and globally recognized Rijksmuseum has failed to establish processes of ionization in their exhibits. As of January 2024, there was a single room in the massive space, displaying together voyeuristic and exploitative paintings of indigenous people alongside each other with inadequate context. This display of art, likely stolen artifacts and paintings designed by European artists (without any intention of compensating, or recognizing the indigenous models) is a failure to acknowledge the truly abhorrent nature of colonialism. The glorification of European colonialism creates two things. It fails to recognize the beauty of the already established lives and cultures of people residing in non-European areas, and it also enforces a single narrative of history, when, in reality, it is a responsibility of historians to capture the most complete truth of events in the past – including recording and amplifying as many voices as possible to garner a wide array of perspectives including indigenous voices. When the narrative

of the past simply repeats the story of white, Protestant, European, Dutch colonizers, historians and future generations might fail to see the complexity of faith, identity, ethics, and priorities among the globalizing world.

History is not simply names and dates, nor should it be interpreted as separate periods of events, digested as isolated eras in time. Rather, history is a vast spiderweb, networking and connecting the world and patterns and similarities. Since the colonial period, it is impossible and irresponsible to consider the policies and developments of one country, such as the Netherlands, without establishing, and considering their global network facilitating such designs.

The shift in historiography and analysis allows historians to recognize newly discovered patterns and explanations, for how, and why events of the past unfolded in their particular manner. Through an intersection and interdisciplinary lens, the support of Jewish community can be understood through many disciplines. For instance, they were undoubtedly a persecuted minority during the reconquest and expulsion from Spain and later Portugal. They were also a small minority in the Netherlands, but afforded great allowances of religious toleration and economic freedom due to the Dutch beliefs in laissez-faire economics and anti-Spanish and anti-Catholic sentiment. This project would not be complete without discussing the hierarchy of power and race, especially in the colonial holdings. They were minorities who were considered racially “other” than European, who undeniably benefited, socially, and economically from their colonial involvement. While it’s unlikely to be completely certain, it is important to consider that participating in colonialism likely was a way for this community to climb the hierarchy of power. By oppressing indigenous people through colonization, and being active participants in the

colonial project, the group could have gained authority and status/security, by being perceived as closer to the standard of whiteness. The modern implications of this research project are both cerebral and physical. That colonial style architecture is undoubtedly a prominent aspect of the modern effects of migration and colonization. Through creation of infrastructure the Sephardic Jewish legacy continues to live on.

Additionally, it is evident through modern canal and street signs of the legacy of choosing colonialism. For instance, the street “Spinozahof” located south of Artis in central Amsterdam, dedicates a highly dense area with tourism to the famous Sephardic Jewish philosopher.

The feature of the urban landscape is a wide debate consisting of opposing beliefs, with many definitions of what constitutes a successful landscape. Which is most important, however, that the city should serve the people and not vice versa of pedestrians altering or straining their everyday lived experience to be forced to spend their lives navigating an inefficient city.

It is incredibly valuable to build efficient cities with equally functional and aesthetic architecture. Each resident of the city holds the right and responsibility to ensure an equitable and successful design that values the lives of its residence. Not only does this extend to accessible and affordable public transportation, but the design of building themselves

People deserve communities that nurture a sense of belonging. The Dutch Jewish Cultural Quarter is a great example of a successfully integrated cultural hub, which honors its history, and continues to serve the people. Located in the heart of Amsterdam and within walking distance of the University of Amsterdam, this historic neighborhood housing the Esnoga is a

testament to the preservation and intentional shaping of an efficient third space fostering a strong sense of community.

It is also important to simultaneously recognize and celebrate the continual perseverance and existence of the Portuguese synagogue as an Orthodox temple still standing today. Despite remaining an even smaller minority after the Ashkenazi western migration, and later Holocaust, the Jewish people have persisted and thrive in the Cultural Quarter of Amsterdam. The analysis will continue in a second volume to be published in the future.

Figure 2: Mudéjar Style Architecture, Toledo Synagogue

Figure 3: Toledo Synagogue Cinquefoils and Calligraphy

Figure 4: Toledo Synagogue Judaica

Figure 5: Kahal Zur Israel Synagogue, Recife, Brazil

Figure 6: Mikvé Israel-Emanuel Synagogue, Curaçao

Figure 7: Map of Amsterdam, 1544

Figure 8: Map of Amsterdam, 1649 (Plague)

Figure 9: Netherlands Atlas, circa 1650

Figure 10: Amsterdam, 1770

Figure 11: Amsterdam, 1830-1842

Figure 13: Grave Marker of Jeronimo Nunes da Costa

Figure 14: Amsterdam's Portuguese Synagogue

Figure 15: Modern Photograph of Portuguese Synagogue

Figure 16: Modern Interior of Portuguese Synagogue

Figure 17: Modern View of Amsterdam's Architecture and Canals

Figure 18: Spinozahof Street Sign

Figure 19: Amsterdam Centraal

Figure 20: Brasil Koffie (Het Koffie Cultuur Centrum)

Figure 21: William of Orange, Den Haag

Figure 22: Mauritshuis Exterior (1/2)

Figure 23: Mauritshuis Exterior (2/2)

Mauritshuis

Koninklijk Kabinet van Schilderijen
Royal Picture Gallery

Het gebouw

Het Mauritshuis werd tussen 1633 en 1644 gebouwd als woonhuis voor Johan Maurits van Nassau-Siegen. Tijdens de bouw was hij gouverneur van Nederlands-Brazilië, een kolonie die draaide om suiker en slavernij. Het geld dat Johan Maurits er verdiende, gebruikte hij voor de bouw van zijn Haagse woning.

De architect van het Mauritshuis is Jacob van Campen. Zijn ontwerp is een van de eerste en puurste voorbeelden van wat we het Hollands classicisme noemen. De symmetrie, de hoge pilasters en de tympanen aan de gevels zijn gebaseerd op de bouwkunst van de Grieken en de Romeinen. En geven het gebouw zijn monumentale allure.

Het Mauritshuis had een indrukwekkend interieur met betimmeringen van tropisch hout, muurschilderingen van Braziliaanse landschappen en grote hoeveelheden voorwerpen die Johan Maurits uit Brazilië had meegevoerd. Maar in 1704 ging het interieur verloren tijdens een vernietigende brand. Het huis werd gerestaureerd en kreeg een nieuw interieur. Een eeuw later - in 1822 - werd het ingericht als museum.

The Building

The Mauritshuis was built between 1633 and 1644 as a private residence for Johan Maurits of Nassau-Siegen. During its construction, he was the governor of Dutch Brazil, a colony that was based around sugar and slavery. He used the money that he earned there to build his house in The Hague.

The architect behind the Mauritshuis was Jacob van Campen. His design was one of the first and purest examples of what is known as Dutch Classicism. The symmetry, tall pilasters and tympanums on the façades are based on the architecture of the Greeks and Romans, lending the building its monumental air.

The Mauritshuis had an impressive interior with paneling made of tropical wood, murals depicting Brazilian landscapes and large quantities of objects that Johan Maurits had brought back with him from Brazil. But in 1704 the interior was destroyed during a devastating fire. The house was refurbished and given a new interior. A century later - in 1822 - it became a museum.

Figure 24: Mauritshuis Description

Figure 25: Johan Maurits Private Collection (Frans Post)

Figure 26: Johan Maurits Description

Figure 27: Frans Post, *Brazilian Landscape with a House Under Construction*

Figure 28: Frans Post Description

Figure 29: Rembrandt, *Twee Afrikaanse mannen*

Figure 30: Nootmuskaat (Albert Heijn)

Figure 31: Belize Street Sign

Figure 32: Curaçao Street Sign

Figure 33: *Still Life with a Turkey Pie*. (1627). [Pieter Claesz] Rijksmuseum, Amsterdam, Netherlands.

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About the Author

Natalya Rowe will graduate *summa cum laude* in Spring of 2025 with a Bachelor of Arts in History with a minor in Art as a first generation scholar. She served as a President's Scholar, University Honors resident, Mellon Mays Undergraduate Fellow, Phi Alpha Theta History Honors Society member, Sally Casanova Pre-Doctoral Scholar, and secretary of President's Scholars Student Association. Natalya conducted field work in Amsterdam on the Council on the International Educational Exchange, culminating into three senior projects researched under the supervision of Dr. Paulo Simoes, which explore the relationship of Dutch Sephardic Jews to architecture and the broader global colonial project. After graduation, Natalya plans to pursue a PhD in History, and return back to higher academia to diversify the professoriate.